

Table S1. Age data used for the preferred OxCal posterior age model excluding OSL sample UWLL1298. For details of OSL and radiocarbon dates refer to Tables 1 and 2 , respectively, in the main body of the manuscript text. R_Combine RC12 is combination of the two dates presented in Table 2.

Name	Unmodelled Age (yr BP)		Uncertainties	Modelled Age (yr BP)		Uncertainties
	from	to	%	from	to	%
2016						
Boundary E6	-65	-66	95.4	-65	-66	95.4
E5				4467	-60	95.4
R_Combine RC12	4804	4447	95.4	4804	4447	95.4
C_Date WLL1300	9097	6303	95.4	8002	5626	95.4
Sequence Unit8						
E4				8589	6007	95.4
C_Date USU2903	8145	3355	95.4	9095	6469	95.4
C_Date WLL1299	12295	8305	95.4	10326	7632	95.4
Sequence Unit 6C						
E3				10918	8059	95.4
E2				11450	8561	95.4
C_Date USU2902	11185	7655	95.4	11892	9125	95.4
Phase Unit 2 Top						
E1				15306	9836	95.4
C_Date WLL1297	18095	12106	95.4	17046	11569	95.4
Phase Unit 2 Bottom						
Boundary Base				20490	11799	95.4